

Operationalization Matrix of Variables

Variable	Dimension	Category	Subcategory	Indicator	Items	Scale
Mental Models of Environmental Awareness	Epistemological	Environmental Knowledge	- Use of scientific theories in environmental problems - Pollution - Deforestation - Climate change - Waste management	Knowledge of environmental issues	1 - 7	Ordinal / Interval 1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Somewhat disagree 4. Neutral 5. Somewhat agree 6. Agree 7. Strongly agree
		Knowledge Valuation	- Knowledge valuation - Practical application - Relevance in daily life	Belief in the importance of environmental knowledge		
		Sources of Information	- Media - Formal education - Local communities	Sources of environmental information		
	Ontological	Human–Nature Relationship	- Exploitation of nature - Lack of balance - Interdependence - Harmony	Perception of the human–nature relationship	8 - 12	
		Valuation of Nature	- Resource conservation - Ecological importance - Impact on daily life	Valuation of nature		
		Consequences of Environmental Damage	- Global warming - Biodiversity loss - Health impacts - Scarcity	Awareness of the consequences of environmental damage		
	Cognitive-Linguistic	Use of Environmental Language	- Environmental terms - Expression of concern - Effective communication	Expression of language related to environmental issues	13 - 16	
		Solutions to Environmental Problems	- Concern about pollution - Interest in solutions - Environmental activism	Expression of concern for environmental issues		
		Communication of Solutions	- Action proposals - Information dissemination - Awareness-raising	Ability to communicate environmental solutions		

Variable	Dimension	Category	Subcategory	Indicator	Items	Scale
	Motivational	Willingness to Act	- Concrete actions - Community participation - Intrinsic motivation	Willingness to act in favor of the environment	17- 21	
		Intrinsic Motivation	- Nuclear family - Extended family - Multinuclear family	Influence of internal factors on motivation		
		Extrinsic Motivation	- Education - Public policies - Social influence	Influence of external factors on motivation		

Source: Author